

Extracting data for OxCal from mixSIAR

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```
library(knitr)
hook_output = knit_hooks$get('output')
knit_hooks$set(output = function(x, options) {
  # this hook is used only when the linewidth option is not NULL
  if (!is.null(n <- options$linewidth)) {
    x = xfun::split_lines(x)
    # any lines wider than n should be wrapped
    if (any(nchar(x) > n)) x = strwrap(x, width = n)
    x = paste(x, collapse = '\n')
  }
  hook_output(x, options)
})
```

Get Chinchá data in mixSIAR-ready form.

```
chinchá_indiv_small <- read.csv("remixsiaroxcaltranslator/peru_consumer_small.csv")

###Load Consumer Data for Individual Burials###
mix <- load_mix_data(filename = "remixsiaroxcaltranslator/peru_consumer_small.csv",
  iso_names = c("d13C", "d15N"),
  factors = "Individual",
  fac_random = FALSE,
  fac_nested = NULL,
  cont_effects = NULL)

###Load Source Data from Peru###
source <- load_source_data(filename = "remixsiaroxcaltranslator/peru_sources.csv",
  source_factors = NULL,
  conc_dep = FALSE,
  data_type = "raw",
  mix)

###Load Trophic Enrichment Factor Corrections###
discr <- load_discr_data(filename = "remixsiaroxcaltranslator/peru_discrimination.csv", mix)
```

Set up mixSIAR model.

```
###Plot Consumer and Source Data with TEF Corrections###
plot_data(filename = "isospace_plot",
  plot_save_pdf = F,
  plot_save_png = FALSE,
```

```

        mix, source, discr)

###Set Uniformed/Generalist Prior###
plot_prior(alpha.prior = 1, source, plot_save_pdf = F)

##
## -----
## *** NOTE ***
##
## MixSIAR sorts the sources alphabetically. If you are using an informative
## prior, please check the plot to confirm that the sources you meant to give
## greater weight in the alpha vector receive greater weight in the prior.
## -----

###Create Model File and Set Process Error for Individuals###
model_filename <- "remixsiaroxcaltranslator/MixSIAR_model.txt"
resid_err <- FALSE
process_err <- TRUE

#uncomment next line to (re)write model specs
# write_JAGS_model(model_filename, resid_err, process_err, mix, source)

```

Run model (really should do this outside of .Rmd and read in results, just to avoid running it over and over again).

```

###Run Model###
jags.1 <- run_model(run="normal", mix, source, discr, model_filename, alpha.prior=1)

###Create and Save Standard Outputs###
#set option to save return an object and not save out any images
output_options <- list(return_obj = TRUE, plot_post_save_pdf = F, plot_pairs_save_pdf = F)
output_JAGS(jags.1, mix, source, output_options)

###Attach JAGS Output to Create Histograms###
attach.jags(jags.1)

## save model results
save(jags.1, file = "chincha_jags1.RData")

```

Examine results.

```

#output posteriors

chincha_post <- output_posteriors(jags.1, mix, source, output_options)
names(chincha_post)
chincha_post$fac1 #one plot per individual

save(chincha_post, file = "chincha_post.RData")

```

Read in saved posterior plots.

```
load(file = "chincha_jags1.RData")
load(file = "chincha_post.RData")

(chincha_post$fac1[[1]] | chincha_post$fac1[[2]]) /
  (chincha_post$fac1[[3]] | chincha_post$fac1[[4]])
```


p.fac1 is the diet proportion by Individual, indexed as [MCMC chain, Individual, Source].

Check how source names map onto the factors, since we want to pull only the marine fraction for each individual.

```
source$source_names # marine = source 3
```

```
## [1] "C3"          "C4"          "Marine"     "Terrestrial"
```

```
#so
```

```
propMarine <- jags.1$BUGSoutput$sims.list$p.fac1[, , 3] #all draws, all individuals, proportion Marine
#produces a column for each individual
```

```
#compare these to posterior plots from mixSIAR to make sure that we're getting the right data
ind1 <- data.frame(propMarine = propMarine[,1], Ind = "Individual 1, marine")
```

```
ggplot(data = ind1, aes(x = propMarine)) +
  geom_density(alpha = 0.3, aes(y = ..scaled..)) +
  theme_bw() +
```

```
labs(x = "Proportion", y = "Scaled Posterior Density",  
      title = "Individual 1, Proportion Marine") +  
xlim(0,1)
```



```
chinchu_post$fac1[[1]] +  
  geom_density(data = ind1, alpha = 0.3,  
               aes(x = propMarine, y = ..scaled.., linetype = Ind), inherit.aes = F) +  
  scale_linetype_manual(values = 2)
```


#success!

Now build a function that will pull information for each individual and output OxCal code. Inputs are the output of `mixSIAR::output_posteriors()` and a dataframe that can be used to relate the number of each individual to the burial ID.

```

mixcalplot <- function(mixSIAR_output, individuals) {
  ks <- vector("list", length = ncol(mixSIAR_output))
  vals <- vector("list", length = ncol(mixSIAR_output))
  oxcalstring <- vector("list", length = ncol(mixSIAR_output))

  i <- 1
  for (i in 1:ncol(mixSIAR_output)){
    ks[i] <- ks.test(mixSIAR_output[,i], "pnorm")$p.value
    names(ks)[i] <- paste(individuals %>% filter(Individual == i) %>% select(Burial),
                          "KS test p.value")

    vals[i] <- data.frame(probs = round(hist(mixSIAR_output[,i],
                                           breaks = seq(min(mixSIAR_output[,i]), max(mixSIAR_output[,i]),
                                                         length.out = 101), plot = F)$density, 2))
    #re-associate with burial names; note that variable names will need to match input object
    names(vals)[i] <- individuals %>% filter(Individual == i) %>% select(Burial)

    oxcalstring[i] <- paste0('Mix_Curves("Mix for ', names(vals)[i],
                              ', "SHCal20", "LocalMarine", P(-1,101,[0,',
                              paste(vals[[i]], collapse = ","), ',0]));')
  }
}

```

```

}

list(ks, vals, oxcalstring)
}

```

That function produces a list that includes the p-value of a K-S test, the densities of a histogram with 100 bins, and the 'Mix_Curves' code for the posterior proportion marine calculated by **mixSIAR** for each individual.

```

chinchamarine_props <- mixcalplot(propMarine, chinchaindiv_small)

cat(unlist(chinchamarine_props[[3]]))

```

```

## Mix_Curves("Mix for JUC_12", "SHCal20",
"LocalMarine",
P(-1,101, [0,1.54,2.35,2.08,1.66,2.35,1.81,2.58,3.04,2.74,2.43,2.77,2.77,2.85,3.04,2.54,2.77,3,2.93,3.12
Mix_Curves("Mix for JUC_17", "SHCal20",
"LocalMarine",
P(-1,101, [0,3.7,3.84,4.32,3.42,3.05,2.84,2.74,2.4,2.64,1.99,3.19,2.36,2.36,1.78,1.99,2.09,1.4,1.71,1.71
Mix_Curves("Mix for JUC_20", "SHCal20",
"LocalMarine",
P(-1,101, [0,3.87,2.65,2.99,3.46,2.38,2.31,2.11,2,1.77,1.6,1.66,1.94,1.56,1.83,1.7,1.66,1.32,1.56,1.8,1.
Mix_Curves("Mix for JUC15", "SHCal20",
"LocalMarine",
P(-1,101, [0,4.1,4.41,4.17,4.2,3.78,4.41,3.47,3.29,3.47,2.77,2.87,3.01,2.24,2.14,2.45,2.87,2.1,2.14,2.24

```

```

#write out as .csv (uncomment the next line)
# write.csv(unlist(chinchamarine_props[[3]]), "chinchamarine_props.csv", row.names = F)

#or copy to clipboard (uncomment the next line)
# clipr::write_clip(unlist(chinchamarine_props[[3]]))

```